

WAYS TO INCLUDE THE ELEMENTS OF SPEECH CULTURE IN THE SPEECH OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: *The article discusses the formation of speech culture in preschool children, the development of children's speech activity.*

Key words: *speech culture, communication, linguistics, pure linguistics, modern linguistics, emotional relations, joint activity, sound relation, communicative factor, intelligence.*

Developing a child's speech during preschool age is one of the most important tasks in education, because teaching the mother tongue prepares the ground for the development of the child's mind and the all-round development of the personality. The child receives social education in the kindergarten, he plays, he works as hard as he can in the team. Appreciating his actions teaches him to notice. One of the forms of education for a child is educational games. The game form of education is the main method from an early age. Children's perception is developed through educational games and activities, they provide age-appropriate information, and form some important qualities and skills.

The educator plans educational games and activities based on "educational and educational programs in kindergarten". Educational game is an important process for mental education of children. During the training, the qualities necessary for the mental development of children are formed, that is, the ability to focus attention, the actions shown, the words spoken are created.

By drawing children's attention and arousing interest, the educator establishes the importance of curiosity, which is one of the main qualities of mental development. A child who has learned to carefully look at objects shown to adults will have a certain amount of knowledge. , he learns the shape, color, size, weight, quality of the material and its properties. His perception develops and is satisfied.

Through educational games, children can learn information about the objects and events of their surroundings. Such educational games are also important for moral education of children. They gradually develop the skills of showing superiority among their peers. First, he learns to do something in the presence of other children without disturbing them, without taking away toys, and without being distracted by other things. Later, they teach to show activity together with other children: they see toys, pictures, animals together, dance together, walk, etc.

For the first time in the child, interest in the actions of another child creates moods of mutual joy. During the training, qualities such as self-restraint, organization and striving for the goal begin to form in children. They develop and improve skills such as being careful with the picture of the toy. At an early age, attitude towards others plays a big role. He observes educational materials and toys with interest. At this age, interest in the work of adults and the desire to participate in their activities begin to form.

Similarly, training plays a big role in shaping aesthetic education in children. Educational materials should serve the purpose of choosing toy paintings, equipping them, and educating children to appreciate good and beautiful things. It is important to remember that training should create a good mood in children. The good mood and feelings of joy that arise in children during training are the basis for the temporary development of the child's speech in the early years and will be of great importance for the educator in the future.

In order for educational games and activities to be interesting and for the temporary implementation of tasks related to the development of speech, the educator should follow the following educational requirements. Educational games and exercises are organized according to the plan. The teacher should thoroughly study the section related to the development of speech from the "Kindergarten Education Program" in advance, and in the distribution of the material, the educational principle of moving from simple to complex will be followed. Successful implementation of work tasks and content in the program requires repetition of training. Training can be repeated from two to four times a day. Work one-on-one with children who are still struggling after repetition. This method avoids excessive repetition with all the children in the group and prevents boredom

Conducting training in an emotional and effective way.

Even after all the children in the group have acquired solid knowledge and skills by repeating the lesson, it is necessary to maintain their interest in the lesson. Therefore, the teacher's voice should be cheerful, sincere, enthusiastic, and the objects used in the training should be attractive (bright colors, unbroken, beautiful). One of the main educational principles is the compatibility of instruction with words. It is said by showing things to children; "Now I will take the iron and iron the shirt" about the action of "doll, teddy bear, doll, cube, nest, etc." With his words, the educator directs the child's attention to the features and quality of the object. By telling the name, characteristic, quality, action of the teacher's subject, the children have an interaction between the reality and the subject and the word that represents them.

Creating an opportunity for children to be active during the lesson. For example; the teacher tells the children about the bird in the cage. At the end of the lesson, he asks to show the children how the bird flies. With this, the educator allows the children to walk around the room with their hands spread out. Duration of training. How long the training lasts depends on the activity of the children during the training and their emotional state. If the teacher notices signs of fatigue in the children (their activity decreases, they start to get distracted by other things quickly), they should end the training and give the children the opportunity to move freely and play.

Training and educational games will be successful only when they are organized correctly. Training and games are held during a special time that is separated in daily order; It is used in the morning after breakfast, during a walk, after the afternoon nap, after the children have finished eating, and with babies who sleep twice a day, during the second cry. Taking into account the age and personal characteristics of children is also of great importance in the correct design of training and educational games.

The development of speech activity in preschool children is a complex mental process, which does not consist only in imitating the speech heard by the child. This is primarily due to the fact that children have a need for communication if they want to develop communication activities in general. The child's orientation to new aspects of existence: the transition from

practical activities to studying the world, and then people, their relationships, creates the need for new means of communication that serve new purposes. Expanding the child's lexicon creates an opportunity for him to master a wider and more diverse expression of his experiences.

In order to develop the child's speech in a modern and complete way, it is necessary to enrich the content of the child's need for communication through interaction with the people around him. The reason why children acquire speech is that the basis of their communication activities is the need-motivation, and its structure has changed. In the process of verbal management in kindergarten, children's speech is formed slowly. So, the main importance of the period in this stage is that the necessary conditions are created for them to move to the next stage - the stage of the emergence of active speech. In the second stage of the child's acquisition of active speech, three main aspects are distinguished. They are the following:

- ❖ *emotional relationships;*
- ❖ *joint activity, i.e. cooperation, continuous relations;*
- ❖ *sound relations.*

Each aspect of the communicative factor considered to one degree or another helps children to solve the communicative task, that is, to use speech. In the third stage of speech development - the subject of the child, lexicon and grammar, mastering the task of communication of the child. depends on the need for communication with and its content. This leads to the acquisition of new, more complex and comprehensive aspects of the child's speech. The fact that speech occupies a decisive place in the child's mental formation increases the importance of the conditions and factors that help his development at different stages. Determining the forces that stimulate or slow down the development of children's speech is the key to organizing pedagogical actions with a clear goal in this process.

The child's life will be adapted to the life activities of adults. At this time, the child does not need any specific human means to influence him. The main genetic task of this development is to form the ability and means of communicating with an adult in children. The ability of a preschool educator to teach children his native language is an important indicator of his professional training. All mental abilities given to a child by nature appear and develop due to mastering the mother tongue, especially learning it at preschool age.

The extent to which children can inherit the national spiritual wealth that is passed from generation to generation in their mother tongue, the ability of the children to master the scientific achievements of their time in the future, their loyalty to the advanced poetic and aesthetic ideals of humanity, that is, independent A child in kindergarten plays with his friends and works as hard as he can. In this process, he learns to evaluate his actions, to express his thoughts in a way that is understandable to others. Through observation and speech, the child learns about the world, existence, learns to tell the names, qualities and signs, characteristics, similarities and differences of surrounding things and objects, events and phenomena.

CONCLUSION.

The mother tongue plays a key role in solving important and vital tasks, such as increasing the effectiveness of education in kindergarten, preparing children for independent education, that is, educating conscious builders of society. It is necessary to pay great attention to the development of children's speech through the use of didactic materials in speech

development activities. Educational games are one of the main methodologies (methods) of activating children's vocabulary.

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